

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FORMATION OF A CULTURE OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN THE FAMILY

A.I.Saidov

Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

Psychology doctor of science (DSc), associate professor

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Abstract. *The article deals with the problems of the psychology of a healthy lifestyle in the family, its formation and possible social and psychological ways to solve these problems. Illuminated, scientific and practical results of research related to healthier lifestyle of the individual.*

Key words: *Healthy generation, family, upbringing, mental health, physical, family sports.*

СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КУЛЬТУРЫ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ В СЕМЬЕ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются проблемы психологии здорового образа жизни в семье, ее формирования и возможные социально-психологические пути решения этих проблем. Освещены научные и практические результаты исследований, связанных со здоровым образом жизни человека.*

Ключевые слова: *здоровое поколение, семья, воспитание, психическое здоровье, физическая культура, семейный спорт.*

INTRODUCTION

A healthy generation is the dream of our ancestors coming to us in the holy aspiration. Our fathers generation of healthy, physically strong, spiritually refreshing, thoughtful thinking ability, I believe-the whole of religion, educated, high moral character, courage and brave papers-those who dream of girls. Worth mentioning, in the years of independence in our country began the realization of the old dream of our ancestors.

From nurturing the spiritual and ethical aspects of young people in them, the principles of psychology of a healthy lifestyle of the mechanisms of psychological development and technical support on the basis of philosophical, psychological, pedagogical, legal and social system on the basis of the approach to develop and improve, harmoniously developed generation, the role of civil society and educational institutions and taking into account the psychology of youth in the family formation in the neighborhood of a healthy lifestyle, psychological, and educational institutions further strengthening of cooperation of civil society, the psychology of science that requires scientific research as one of the pressing issues in front of you.

Today which is the foundation of a healthy lifestyle psychic health over the short term is the fact that it has not become a major in the field of studies. We should note that this position is proving the following numbers. A year 1975 gar AThe electoral "lapses" in the program was applied to 200 psychic related to the protection of health, if such programs have come to 1990 increased to 5000. In the present day shows they are significant economic efficiency [1]. Awhen The electoral "lapses" it's one in every ten persons or Beijing psychic health psychologist engaged with this problem, as well as English-speaking psychological journals associated with each article as published in this area, one from three, it should be recognized that various aspects of [2].

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

About the word go since healthy lifestyle, which primarily cause harmful habits of being than man and check his imagine to be forgive have left to learn. This is a term primarily associated with the activities of health workers in a manner explained. But, in the formation of healthy lifestyle - recognize the body and directly into mind and perception, human psychology and cognitive science of psychology secrets related to her election to be also there is a connection to him. Accordingly, in the science of psychology is understanding the psychology of a healthy lifestyle there to a healthy lifestyle, above all, does not look as a reflection of the human mind and thinking. Therefore, it is necessary for each of us to achieve our health and a healthy lifestyle to ensure water and make the habit not only to the medical staff, but also of psychology, the research also appears as the subject of the science of psychology.

In this sense, psychology healthy lifestyle in the formation of the human temperament, manners, and when studied from the perspective of various psychological conditions: basically, each of us spiritual vision ourselves as secret as healthy-health, how to feel that there are trigger and related aspects of it management through our own rich – how the availability of opportunities we have in our hands in order to maintain our health, our mental state and the formation of a healthy lifestyle every one of our own psychology, management, awareness of the changes underway at the time to keep it moderate, ways to adapt to changing conditions in this area, studies are increasingly confident that entered our lives as a useful preventive science and practice.

And finally, the new year on a healthy lifestyle to the psychological aspects of human character; the person's attitude toward a healthy lifestyle; and the new year of a healthy lifestyle social-psychological factors of individual-psychological characteristics of the person grow the effects of family environment, that is, you can add the external factors.

As noted in the source, the direction of the medical staff taking the various factors considered to be a fantasy a healthy lifestyle, and will recommend him to live follow [3]. is not only biological factors on human health, but living in the social environment, person himself, also interact with the surrounding people to communicate related. In human relationships, first of all, from the family, from the family environment begins. To follow a healthy lifestyle does not suddenly become visible in live human skills, it is also specific in that regard, qualification requirements for early childhood in the family should teach him. This is the most important responsibility of parents, is one of the tasks responsible. All parents educate their children , and to be constantly aware, alert adheres to stand. All the things that the child's attention enough, and a place of good health, may not remain confined to attend their regular lessons briefly as control norms. Above all, the main centers of human life - the healthy lifestyle of the family should[4].

RESEARCH RESULTS

As it is known, family - each mini of this society. As a part of the family and social life of society, there are specific functions, which in turn responsibility to be certain that you have the knowledge of every one of these tasks, and most importantly puts the requirement to feel. Agarda family or of society as a structured piece “the tumor” if you go in spiritually and spiritual development, especially if a clear sign of mutual responsibilities and the interests of the parties in the family gets of the family will not be such a prosperous future. Therefore, a successful family norms, that is, algorithm or a sign of something before we should give importance to provide the template.

The most complex group of the family is from. It not only serious approach to the construction of those that viewed the family meticulous with each other, but also later during the whole life almost every day, every hour, stuck to one another in deep if you need a life partner think of the relationship requires. Only then the family happy, healthy and lasts long. Accordingly, a successful family model (module) determines all aspects of the template to create a healthy lifestyle you need to identify the out. Potential of each spouse separately, then this template should find practical mechanisms that may contribute to performance, that is, necessary to identify ways to create a prosperous family, in other words, it is necessary to develop algorithms. Thus, spiritual; psychological; physical; medical aspects should be taken considering.

The spiritual aspect of the norms - both for both men and women the same, the positive qualities of the family should be based on providing the wellbeing of: the level of knowledge, level educated, responsible, corresponding to one of outlook, culture, a sense of aspiration to improve.

The psychological aspects of the norm can be manifested in the following qualities; tolerance, i.e. joint, moral and polite in. should be cultivated in the form of gentleness, always eager to impress must escape from. Algorithm the algorithm directly associated with spiritual spiritual the form of norms, and in many ways to the education of the young stems.

Legal aspects of physical - physically pursuing perfection in halls, gym, fitness and lifestyle motivational health go to the club to stand and sustain physical action that is identified in the development of philosophy from the perspective of the factors to take into account is necessary.

DISCUSSION

Legal aspects of medical - primarily the detection of various diseases, especially the which was or social injuries (tb, ids, sexually transmitted diseases) should be directed to determine. But we have to approach from the other side and positive norms of future spouse must be encouraged to be responsible for their health. Well, how can you achieve the specified results and build a successful family norms? Ways and mechanisms of a healthy lifestyle or psychology algorithm the system is based on a gradual and growing generation is determined on the basis of goal-oriented education. The process of governmental, non-governmental and public organizations, most importantly, without the involvement of educational institutions can achieve positive results. Starting from kindergarten, schools, lyceums, colleges and universities have also realized the importance of the organization of the church the importance of neighborhood will influence the formation of prosperity in the family because that's exactly where it should be. Along with this, the youth between positive norms in the formation of the traditions of our people, our mentality, customs and traditions passed from generation to generation of our family every need to focus on coming. Athe respect in the education of the young generation is a large ointment.

Authorities spiritual formation among young people - complex and versatile, this specific diseases, or the family he to himself, proceeding from conditions of environment, the approach is a process that requires. To the issue of spirituality in the education of the young generation in the country is given great importance. "Spiritual enlightenment" is the center of a "family research-applied research" centers and neighborhood business remain effective despite the fact that the issue of spirituality in the education of the young generation on the state level, and all education institutions of age spiritually perfect in a position to be an adult, they should be responsible for.

Also, a potential life partner in building a successful family also corresponds to a mental state of one of it should be noted that is very significant. According to noted in psychological practice in this regard is shown to explain the works of the need, it also young people (future spouse) during a certain time of each other learn each other better and for obtaining their individual qualities should determine concerning the work of the meeting must be some explanation.

Dear friends, as you know Uzbekistan in the formation of healthy lifestyle of the family, more family (women)related to: physical culture of connection to family members, ministry, children mode of training (the procedure, diet, dress, culture, leisure, manufacturing, lesson).

In this regard, also, the actual health of the population in the country today and to enhancing the importance of physical education which is the source of all places to go to his family to attracting women to achieve access to this work – family of sports promotion period requirements.

Family sports deal with, primarily, those families that strong, sarishta ensures the welfare ministry and the central election commission. The health of family members of all ages in a family with such strong spiritual environment chinese state is regularly a good relationship, each member of the family, to study, to work with high passion, the mood is always good. Ain the same family is not, nor kindness, kindness is not the responsibility we have, the attention is usually the case.

The recovery tool is not only of physical education and sports of the population, but the optimal organization of production of leisure, of the general human culture, the culture of other people dealing with the factors that shape the spiritual development of the younger generation also. Health and physical education in solving social problems, and not only sports, but the population (especially young people) between the spiritual and physical environment means that there are put the oven is unhealthy. Physical education (sports), and himself in the young men who make a habit of “empty time” to the place remains.

CONCLUSION

Note that in order to achieve a positive result, further work in this direction in our country, enhancing all kinds of healthy lifestyle among the population mass media and the general public on a regular basis, using power from a wide targeted propaganda to make the importation of sports equipment to the family, in the neighborhood of educational institutions in all the joints of the gym, the time of the landing, complete with the specific requirements of the relevant equipment and the construction and provide, respectively, sports mugs, type of section is represented reproduction of this activity is to be conducted ourselves in training of local personnel, family dealing with sports, and it is propaganda to encourage our members to active members of the society that it would be worthwhile to go.

To conclude, as can be noted, a healthy lifestyle, on the one hand, refers to a person's physical health and fullness, the second on the other hand, the ideological and spiritual health of man, as the basis of his person find the identities of make up. Not only physical, but also social, the spiritual aspect is the only active member of society who feel healthy from himself, and can bring profit to himself, to circumference.

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